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Review Paper

Solubility Enhancement Techniques: A Comprehensive Review of Approaches for Poorly Soluble Drugs

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ABSTRACT

Aqueous solubility is one of the crucial factor that affect drug's bioavailability. In order to achieve the intended pharmacological action, it is crucial to attain the the optimal concentration of the drug in the bloodstream. Almost 50% of the newly discovered drugs are found to be insoluble during the screening phase. Delivery of drugs and formulation development are restricted by poor solubility. Diverse techniques have been explored to improve the drug's water solubility. Since majority of drugs are poorly soluble, this review article focuses mostly on those that fall within classes II and IV of the Biopharmaceutical Classification System (BCS). Several techniques are described to improve the solubility of poorly soluble drugs, including solid dispersions, inclusion complexation, dendrimers, nano-suspensions, co-solvency, pH modification approach, self-emulsifying drug delivery system, hydrotrophy, co-crystallization, and ionic liquid creation.

INTRODUCTION

Solubility is defined as the ability of a solute to dissolve in a particular solvent to form a uniform mixture, resulting in a formation of a solution. A substance's solubility is mostly dependent on the solvent used, temperature, and pressure. A solute's

extent of solubility in a particular solvent can be measured using the saturation concentration. (1)

For many years, researchers have been searching for the ideal approach to make drug more soluble, which increases their bioavailability. Low aqueous solubility is a significant factor affecting

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bioavailability of more than 40 % of newly discovered compounds. This is because, in order for the drug to be able to partition across the membrane of an epithelial cell, it must be present in the solution form in the aqueous intestinal fluid (passive diffusion).(2)

Solubility and permeability are two important aspects of drug absorption. The Biopharmaceutical Classification System is used to classify drugs based on their solubility and permeability.(3) BCS divides the drugs based on their solubility & permeability into four classes. Low solubility characteristic of both class II and IV compounds, but poor permeability is an additional problem for class IV compounds. A drug is considered to have high soluble when its maximum dose strength dissolves in 250 millilitres or less of aqueous medium at 37°C and a pH range of 1-7.5.(4)

Figure 1: BCS CLASSIFICATION

Importance of solubility

Solubility plays a crucial role in any formulation to achieve therapeutic drug concentration for obtaining maximum pharmacological response. Drugs having very low aqueous solubility require higher dose be in to reach therapeutic drug concentration after oral administration. Drug must be in an aqueous solution form for absorption. Water serves as the main solvent when working with liquid formulations.(5)

Most of the weekly acidic and basic drugs have very limited aqueous solubility. Over 40% of new discovered molecules have less water solubility. These poorly soluble drugs are slowly absorbed, cause gastrointestinal mucosal damage and result in insufficient and inconsistent bioavailability. Solubility is the most crucial factor limiting the rate at which oral drugs can reach in appropriate concentration in the blood stream for systemic action. (6)

3. Techniques for Solubility Enhancement

There are various procedures to improve solubility, which can be divided into three categories: physical modification, chemical modification of the drug, and miscellaneous methods.

Table 1: Solubility enhancement Technique

Physical Modification	Chemical Modifications	Other Methods
A. Particle size reduction 1.Micronization 2.Nanosuspension 3.Sonocrystalis ation 4. Supercritical fluid process	A. Complexation 1.Physical Mixture 2.Co-grinding 3.Kneading method 4. Neutralization 5.Spray-Drying Method 6. Irradiation Method 7. Coprecipitate method 8.Lyophilization/Freeze drying	A.Supercritical fluid process B.Micelle solubilization C.Solubilization by surfactants 1.Microemulsions 2.Selfmicroemulsif ying drug delivery systems
B. Modification of the crystal habit	B. Change of pH:	B. Micelle solubilization

	1. Prodrug formation 2. Co-solvency 3. Co-crystallization 4. Hydrotropy	
C. Drug dispersion in carriers 1. The fusion (melt) method 2. The solvent method 3. Dropping method 4. Spray drying techniques 5. Microwave Ir radiation Method 6. Lyophilization/Freeze drying		C. Solubilization by surfactant 1. Microemulsions 2. Selfmicroemulsifying drug delivery systems

1. Physical Method

Solid dispersion method:

The Noyes-Whitney equation is helpful in determining the solubility of poorly aqueous soluble drugs by using the dissolution rate. Dissolution of compound can take place by increasing its surface area and reducing its particle size. Moreover, a faster rate of dissolution will result from making the surface of the compound more wettable. (7)

$$Dc/Dt = AD(C_s - C)/h \dots \dots \dots (1)$$

Mechanism:

In a solid dispersion, a drug's strong intermolecular interactions (such as hydrogen bonds or van der Waals forces) are broken when it is transformed from its crystalline state to an amorphous state. Higher free energy and increased molecular mobility in amorphous forms improve their solubility and pace of dissolution. Hydrophilic carriers, such as HPMC, PVP, or polyethylene glycol (PEG), improve the wettability of the drug in solid dispersions. Better wettability makes it easier for water to enter the solid matrix, which improves solubility. (8)

Various polymer can be employed in this method.

1. Hydrophilic polymer: These types of polymers improve drug solubility by forming water-soluble matrix.

- (A) Polyethylene glycol: Common grades like PEG 4000, 6000 and 8000 are used.
- (B) Polyvinyl pyrrolidone: Common grades like PVP K30 and PVP K90 are used.
- (C) Hydroxypropyl methyl cellulose: Mostly used for controlled release and solubility enhancement. (9)
- (D) Hydroxypropyl cellulose: Used for its thermoplastic and solubilizing properties.

2. Amorphous polymers:

These promote amorphization of drug, increase solubility:

- (A) Eudragit-R (Acrylate polymer): Provides controlled release for enteric coated formulations.
- (B) Kollidon V4 64: It is a vinylpyrrolidone-vinyl acetate copolymer used for amorphous solid dispersion. (9)

3. Biodegradable polymer: These polymers are used when biocompatibility and sustained release are required. E.X.: polylactic acid, polyglycolic acid, poly (lactic-co-glycolic acid)

4. Miscellaneous polymers:

Poloxamers (e.g. poloxamer 188,407) Amphiphilic block copolymers enhancing wetting and solubilization.

Carbomers: Most commonly used as mucoadhesive polymers.(10)

Methods for preparing solid Dispersion:

There are the various method used for preparing solid dispersion mentioned below:

Kneading Technique, Solvent evaporation method, Co-precipitation method, Melting method, Co-grinding method, Gel entrapment technique, Spray-Drying Method, Hot-melt extrusion.(10)

Figure 2: Hot-melt extrusion

E.x:

1. By using solid dispersion technique using hydrophilic polymer there was enhanced dissolution & oral bioavailability of valsartan HCl.(11)

2. Fenofibrate is used in hyperlipidemia which is not soluble in water and low absorption in gastric fluid. By using PEG 6000 as a polymer in solid dispersion technique there was 8 fold increase absorption in biological fluid(0.1 N HCl). (12)

(B) Nano-suspension:

Nan suspensions are preparation consisting of poorly water-soluble drug without any matrix ingredient suspended in dispersion. Nanosuspension of drug that can be prepared by reducing the size (typically less than 1

micron). This leads to enhanced in surface area leading to improved solubility & dissolution rate. (13)

There are numerous approaches to prepare nanosuspensions, including solvent diffusion method and melt dispersion method; these are most commonly used method. Other options include precipitation, microemulsion, high-pressure homogenization, and milling processes.(14)

E.x: Diacerin is a anti-osteoarthritic drug having suboptimal bioavailability by preparing nanosuspension using a high speed homogenization & media milling there was 400 times improvement in bioavailability.(15)

(C) Complexation method

Complexation method is widely used to improve the solubility of low aqueous soluble drugs and it also improve the bioavailability of drug. With a number of case studies, the different types of complexes that enhance the solubility of drug's, dissolution, and permeability. Complexation improves the solubility by forming a soluble complex between poorly soluble drug and complexing agent. complexing agent such as cyclodextrin encapsulate drug molecule in their structure, exposing hydrophilic group to the solvent.(16)

Since cyclodextrins (CDs) have an inherent shape and constitution that makes them advantageous for drugs with low bioavailability and poor water solubility, they are frequently employed in pharmaceutical formulations. CDs act as a carrier used in various drug delivery systems

and can be used to create novel inclusion complexes with enhanced drug solubility.(17) There are basically three types of cyclodextrins- α -cyclodextrin, β -cyclodextrin and γ -cyclodextrin. β -cyclodextrin is the most commonly used cyclodextrin for complex formation to improve solubility of hydrophobic drugs. (18)

Silymarin is a hepatoprotective drug which is having low solubility and oral absorption is about 23-47%. By using complexation(Kneading method) there was 10mg/ml solubility was achieved.(19)

There are many methods that are used for complex formation mentioned below:

Kneading method, co-precipitation method, Solvent evaporation method,freeze drying method.

Figure 3: Inclusion Complexation

(C) Co-solvency method:

Co-solvency is a method that involves blending a drug with a water-miscible solvent to increase its solubility.(20) Co solvents are water-miscible solvents that are frequently employed for solubilization in the pharmaceutical industry.(21) The most often used co-solvent are propylene glycol,ethanol,glycerin and polyethylene glycol.Dimethyl sulfoxide and dimethyl acetamide are common solvent with relative low toxicity and high solubility capacity for poorly soluble drugs.(1)

Co-solvent improves the solubility by following mechanism:

1. Polarity adjustment: Co-solvent alter the polarity of solvent system.This is useful when solute is very poorly soluble in primary solvent(e.g.,water)(21)
2. Hydrogen bonding disruption:In aqueous In a aqueous system co-solvent such as ethanol or propylene glycol can disrupt the structured hydrogen bonding network of water. This reduce the cohesive forces of water ,making it easier for nonpolar or weakly polar solutes to dissolve.(21)
3. Reduction in dielectric constant: Co-solvent reduces the dielectric constant of the solvent

mixture, which can enhance solubility of non-polar or hydrophobic drugs by lowering the solvent's polarity.(21)

Using four distinct cosolvents, the study assessed and evaluated the solubility enhancement of rofecoxib and meloxicam. PEG 400 has proven to be the most effective solubilizing cosolvent and an acceptable cosolvent in terms of side-effect profile, increasing solubility by 778 fold for rofecoxib and about 21 fold for meloxicam at 80% v/v cosolvent level.(22)

Acipimox's solubility in four different solvents like—water, methanol, acetone, and acetonitrile—as well as their aqueous solutions have been determined using the isothermal saturation method at atmospheric pressure and temperatures between 283.15 and 318.15 K. The, the solubility reached its maximum at 80% mass fraction in methanol and acetone aqueous solutions and 60% in acetonitrile aqueous solutions.(23)

(E) Hydrotrophy:

Hydrotrophy is a solubility enhancement technique of poorly water-soluble drug in which large quantity of second solute improve the aqueous solubility of another solute. Different concentrated hydrotropic solution like sodium benzoate, sodium salicylate, urea, nicotinamide, sodium citrate and sodium acetate are observed that improve the aqueous solubility of lipophilic drugs.(24)

Various hypothetical mechanism by which hydrotropes can form:

(I) Self aggregation potential:

Hydrotropes interact strongly with solute and form a complex and these complex would have improved solubility. Hydrotropes also reduce gibbes energy to improve the solubility of solute.

(II) Structure-breaker and structure-maker

A electrostatic force play important role for hydrotropic solubilization for donor-acceptor molecules. Solute which have hydrogen donating and acceptance nature improve the solubility.

Solutropic agent by changing the nature of solvent alter the solvent's ability to structure formation., Urea.

(III) Miceller formation:

It is based on a self-association hydrotropes with a solute which form a micelles. It reduces repulsion between the head group and form a stable micelles.(25)

Classification of hydrotropic agent:

- 1.organic acid and their metal salts
- 2.urea and its derivatives
- 3.Alkaloids
- 4.Phenolic derivatives
5. Surfactants
- 6.Aromatic cations(26)

By using the 8M urea as a hydrotropic agent be 8-fold increase in solubility of ibuprofen that Can be analysed by titrimetric method.(27)

E.x:

1.By using 15% Sodium Salicylate 5% Niacinamide,5% Sodium Acetate 5% Sodium Citrate as a hydrotropic agent 33 fold increase in solubility of furosemide that Can be analysed by titrimetric method.(28)

2.Metronidazole having low solubility & absorption by using urea as a hydrotropic agent &drug in ratio of (15:1) there was 2 fold increase in solubility.(29)

(F) Mixed Hydrotrophy

When two hydrotropic chemical substances are combined there will be combined effect of substances that leads to improve the solubility of drug these phenomena known as mixed Hydrotropy. R.K. Maheshwari created mixed hydrotropy as a solubilization method by using the spectrophotometric examination of a drug having very low aqueous solubility. By using mixed hydrotropic method, the Aceclofenac's solubility was improved 20-40 times in comparison to its solubility in the aqueous phase in solutions containing 45% urea & 45% sodium citrate solution (SCS). Aceclofenac solubility has been improved more than 700 times in a mixed hydrotropic solution with 22.5 percent urea & 22.5 percent sodium citrate. Drugs that are low aqueous solubility that can be dissolved using the mixed hydrotropic solution approach.(30)

Since the hydrotropic technique eliminates the need for emulsion system preparation, organic solvent use, and chemical modification of the drug, it is a promising strategy with tremendous potential for poorly soluble medications. This study's main goal was to boost the oral bioavailability of furosemide by making it more soluble with hydrotropes and their combinations.(31)

Lurasidone HCl is a antipsychotic used in treatment of schizophrenia which having low aqueous solubility. Different hydrotropic agent like nicotinamide, sodium citrate, urea and sodium benzoate at concentration of 10, 20, 30 and 40% w/v solution using water as a solvent.(31)

For decreasing the individual concentration of hydrotropes mixed hydrotropic technique is used. By using mixed hydrotropic agent Nicotinamide + sodium benzoate + sodium citrate in 15:20:5 ratio highest solubility was obtained.(32)

(G)Self-Emulsifying Drug Delivery System:

Self-emulsifying drug delivery system was developed to improve the solubility. SEDDS are isotropic mixture of natural or synthetic oils, solid or liquid surfactant & one or more hydrophilic solvent/co-surfactant.

There are basically two type of SEDDS:

1.Lipid soluble component system: These system is isotropic mixture of lipid and surfactant having HLB value less than 12 that self-emulsify to form fine oil in water emulsion in aqueous medium.

2.Water soluble component system: This system formulated by using hydrophilic surfactant like ethanol, Propylene Glycol & Polyethylene glycols having HLB value greater than 12.

Different oil used for preparing SEDDS like corn oil, olive oil, sesame oil, soyabean oil etc.(33)

Mechanism:

SEDDS when comes into contact with aqueous fluids (e.g., Gastrointestinal fluid, that leads system undergoes spontaneous emulsion formation without need of external energy. This process forms a stable oil-in-water microemulsion or nano emulsion.(34)

There was two main factors small particle size & polarity of oil droplet determine drug release from SEDDS.(35)

Resveratrol is a non-flavonoid having low solubility by preparing SEDDS using various oils, surfactants, and cosurfactants there was increase the solubility. SEDDS prepared from olive oil, Tween 80, and propylene glycol in the ratio 200:266.7:533.3 (in mg) ratio having very increased solubility for oral delivery of resveratrol.(36)

(H)Co-crystals:

Two or more chemically different molecules organized in a stoichiometric ratio to form a multicomponent molecular crystal known as a cocrystal. This type of crystal can be created by modifying drug to change their solubility or other physical characteristics without changing the drugs pharmacological effect.(37)

Mechanism:

The cocrystal having drug and conformer held together in a single crystalline structure via non-covalent interactions. This crystal lattice having lower lattice energy than pure drug enabling faster disruption of the lattice in presence of solvent.(38)

Examples:

- Carbamazepine-saccharin cocrystal: It having significantly improved the solubility of carbamazepine approximately 1.5 to 2 times higher than pure drug. Pure drug having 200ug/ml solubility where as cocrystal having 350-400ug/ml solubility was determined. (39)
- Atorvastatin calcium co-crystals were prepared and characterized utilizing a liquid-assisted grinding process with co-formers such as nicotinamide and citric acid to improve solubility. Atorvastatin calcium's solubility was improved by the co-crystallization approach by employing a liquid-assisted grinding method.(40)

Telmisartan (TMS) an angiotensin-II Receptor antagonist used in treatment of hypertension, dissolves slowly in water due to its low solubility. The telmisartan water solubility and rate of dissolution was increased through the production of TMS-OXA co-crystals.(41)

(I)pH-modification technique

It is possible to change the microenvironment pH at the diffusion area by incorporating a pH-

modifying excipient into the formulation. If drug shows pH-dependent solubility it may dissolve more readily if the pH of the microenvironment is adjusted, which could result in improved oral absorption.(42) (43)

An effective way to modify pH for ionizable drugs is through Adjusting the pH. When ionizable drugs contain basic groups (like amines) or acid groups (like carboxylic acids), they can be protonated or deprotonated, respectively. For an additional boost in solubility, pH adjustment is commonly paired with co-solvents.(42)

Phenytoin injection (Epanutin® ready mixed, Pfizer) 50 mg/ml with propylene glycol 40% and ethanol 10% (1.1 mmol Na⁺ per 5 ml ampoule) is one example of a commercially available product that has been formulated using the pH adjustment approach.(43)

(J)Ionic liquid formation:

Ionic liquid (ILs) has played an important role in polymer chemistry, which possess the desirable property of hydrophobicity/hydrophilicity. A hydrophobic associating polymer was transformed with a polymerizable ionic liquid using free-radical polymerization. The polymer containing ionic liquids demonstrated superior rheological and solubility characteristics compared to the traditional hydrophobic polymer. Moreover, the hydrophilic ionic liquid might improve the rheological characteristics and polarity of the polymer solution.(44)

E.x: A novel ionic liquid solvent was created Using tryptophan as the anion and choline as the cation. After some study, the drug's mechanism for improving solubility was shown not due to pH increase in the medium. The formation of hydrogen bonds and the π - π interaction between aromatic rings are the most important mechanisms responsible for the rise in glibenclamide solubility.(45)

It has been demonstrated that ionic liquids are a suitable solvent for solubilizing an extensive variety of sparingly soluble or insoluble drugs for use in formulations or administration. Many of the disadvantages of solid-state medications, like polymorphism and low solubility, stability, and bioavailability, can also be addressed by the use of ILs. Nevertheless, the primary obstacle to creating IL-based medication formulations and drug delivery methods is that many ILs are intrinsically hazardous.(46)

(K)Dendrimers:

Three distinct elements determine the structure of dendrimers, which are large, highly branched polymers:

(I) initiator core;

(II) internal layer, which consists of repeated generations (units) connected to the initiator core; and

(III) External functional surface

By using a divergent technique, Buhleier et al. (1978) synthesized the first dendrimer. Due to solubility enhancing nature of dendrimer researchers are more motivated to comprehend potential dendrimer-drug interactions.(47)

Due to the high degree of specificity of dendrimer structure, which includes size, branching, density, and surface functioning, dendrimers are perfect for enhancing the aqueous solubility of drugs. Many commercially available drugs, including poly(amidoamine) (PAMAM), poly(propylene imine) (PPI or DAB), and poly(etherhydroxylamine) (PEHAM), have been effectively synthesized with dendrimers to exhibit anticancer, anti-inflammatory, and antibacterial properties.(48)

Dendrimer solubility behavior is impacted by the covalent and non-covalent complexes they form

with drug molecules and hydrophobes. The stability, controlled release, large drug payload, and decreased toxicity of the entrapped drug or drugs are the advantages of dendrimer-mediated complexation. There is an abundance of research on the non-covalent interactions between dendrimers and drugs in terms of solubilization. In contrast to covalent conjugation, non-covalent complexation frequently results in lower drug encapsulation and complex stability.(49)

E.X:Ketoprofen is a NSAID is not freely soluble in water(0.0165 mg/ml) by using polyamidomide dendrimer concentration (10 mg/ml) there was also increase in solubility of ketoprofen 10 mg/ml.(50)

Figure 4: Basic Structure of Dendrimer:

(L)Prodrug Approach:

prodrug is a drug that has been chemically modified to increase its water solubility. After being taken, the prodrug is broken down by the body to release the active ingredient. This method is frequently applied to drugs that are low solubility in lipid and water. One way to change a hydrophobic drug is to transform it into a

hydrophilic ester prodrug, which dissolves better in aqueous solution.(51)

These approaches are employed in drug design to enhance the solubility, stability, bioavailability, and targeting, among other pharmacokinetic and pharmacological aspects of APIs. Prodrugs of several kinds, such as bio precursor and carrier linked prodrugs, were utilized to solubilize drug which having very poor aqueous solubility.(51)

Mechanism of conversion:

1. Enzymatic conversion: Prodrugs are often created to act as substrates for particular enzymes found in the organs' intended tissues. The prodrug becomes the active drug when it comes into contact with the enzyme. As an example, the liver's esterase can break the ester bond and release the drug.(52)

2. Chemical Conversion: Certain prodrugs are made to release the active medication by non-enzymatic hydrolysis or other chemical events that take place in the physiological environment.(52)

E.x:

1.Palmarumycin is drug which having low aqueous solubility 0.1 mg/ml but when these converted into prodrug ester form there will be 7 fold increase in solubility(0.7mg/ml).

2.Acyclovir is a antiviral drug having poor solubility & bioavailability by converting amide prodrug there was 17 fold increase in solubility.(53)

Prodrugs must possess sufficient stability to hold their form both in storage and when they get to the intended tissue or location of action. Unintentional early conversion may result in higher Toxicity or decreased efficacy.(53)

(M)Super-critical fluid Technology:

A sophisticated and adaptable method called supercritical fluid technology is used to increase the aqueous solubility, and bioavailability of drugs having low aqueous solubility. carbon dioxide most commonly used for supercritical fluid. The ability of this approach to manufacture small drugs particles with better solubility is gaining in the pharmaceutical sector.(54)

Principle of Supercritical fluid technology:

Drugs are processed by SCFT in a variety of methods, including as reducing particle size, solubilizing, and forming solid dispersions, by utilizing the unique characteristics of supercritical fluid.

Solvent power: SCFs can change their solvating power in response to variations in temperature and pressure. It allows possible for extraction and selective solubility of compounds.(55)

Method using SCF to improve solubility:

1.Supercritical Anti-solvent 2.Rapid Expansion of Supercritical solution

3.Supercritical fluid extraction of Emulsion(56)

SCF improve solubility by different mechanism:

1. SCFs can be utilized to create ultra-fine medicine particles or nanoparticles by the use of Gas Anti-Solvent (GAS) methods or Rapid Expansion of Supercritical Solutions (RESS).(56)
2. SCFs can solubilize drugs and co-precipitate them with excipients or carriers due to their unique solvent characteristics, particularly scCO₂.(56)

3. Highly porous drug particles can be produced using SCF processing. A greater porosity facilitates better penetration in a dissolution medium, which increased drug release.(57)

E.x:Grisiofulvin having low aqueous solubility(15ug/ml) so by using supercritical fluid trifluoromethane in micronization process there was increase in solubility of grisiofulvin in 100 times much more compare to pure drug.(58)

Challenges and Considerations:

High pressure Requirements: The high pressure need for equipment is required can lead the cost and complexity of procedure.

Drug Compatibility: All drugs are not compatible with supercritical fluids, particularly those that do not dissolve well in SC-CO₂.

Process optimization: Optimal conditions (temperature, pressure, flow rates) for each drugs achieving can be challenging and require extensive experimentation.(58)

CONCLUSION

Improving solubility would be a highly effective way to increase bioavailability for BCS class II drugs. Solubility problems often delay the development of newly produced API. There are numerous methods for improving solubility, and each one enhance the solubility by different mechanism. To increase the drug's solubility, the numerous techniques discussed above can be used alone or in combination with one another.

The benefits and drawbacks of each technique must be considered while choosing the best approach for the drug selection. To reduce the likelihood of errors, it is essential to select the appropriate technique. Academic and corporate research has improved our understanding of how to make drug more soluble through various techniques; this science will help to produce

effective drug formulations for poorly soluble drugs.

REFERENCES

1. Lachman L, Liberman H, Kanig JL. The theory and practice of industrial pharmacy. 3rd ed. Philadelphia: Lea & Febiger; 1986.
2. Lipinski CA. Poor aqueous solubility—an industry wide problem in ADME screening. Pfizer Global Research and Development; 2002.
3. Galia E, Nicolaidis E, Hörter D, Löbenberg R, Reppas C, Dressman JB. Evaluation of various dissolution media for predicting in vivo performance of class I and II drugs. *Pharm Res.* 1998;15(5):698–705.
4. Dahan A, Miller JM, Amidon GL. Prediction of solubility and permeability class membership: provisional BCS classification of the world's top oral drugs. *AAPS J.* 2009;11(4):740–6.
5. Vemula VR, Lagishetty V, Lingala S. Solubility enhancement techniques. *Int J Pharm Sci Rev Res.* 2010;5(1):41–51.
6. Sharma D, Soni M, Kumar S, Gupta GD. Solubility enhancement—eminent role in poorly soluble drugs. *Res J Pharm Technol.* 2009;2(2):220–4.
7. Leuner C, Dressman J. Improving drug solubility for oral delivery using solid dispersions. *Eur J Pharm Biopharm.* 2000;50(1):47–60.
8. Tipduangta P, Chansakaow S, Tansakul P, Meungjai R, Dilokthornsakul P. Polymer matrix and manufacturing methods in solid dispersion system for enhancing andrographolide solubility and absorption: A systematic review. *Pharmaceutics.* 2024;16(5):688.
9. Nair AR, Lakshman YD, Anand VSK, Sree KN, Bhat K, Dengale SJ. Overview of extensively employed polymeric carriers in

- solid dispersion technology. *AAPS PharmSciTech.* 2020;21(5):185.
10. Patel VR, Agrawal YK. Nanosuspension: An approach to enhance solubility of drugs. *J Adv Pharm Technol Res.* 2011;2(2):81–7.
 11. Lakshmi P, Kumar GA. Nanosuspension technology: A review. *Int J Pharm Pharm Sci.* 2010;2(4):35–40.
 12. Hart ML, Do DP, Ansari RA, Rizvi SAA. Brief overview of various approaches to enhance drug solubility. *J Dev Drugs.* 2013;2(03):115.
 13. Xu WJ, Xie HJ, Cao QR, Shi LL, Cao Y, Zhu XY, et al. Enhanced dissolution and oral bioavailability of valsartan solid dispersions prepared by a freeze-drying technique using hydrophilic polymers. *Drug Deliv.* 2016;23(1):41–8.
 14. Patel T, Patel LD, Patel T, Makwana S, Patel T. Enhancement of dissolution of fenofibrate by solid dispersion technique. *Int J Res Pharm Sci.* 2010;1(2):127–32.
 15. Parekh KK, Paun JS, Soniwala MM. Formulation and evaluation of nanosuspension to improve solubility and dissolution of diacerein. *Int J Pharm Sci Res.* 2017;8(4):1643.
 16. Munnangi SR, Youssef AAA, Narala N, Lakkala P, Narala S, Vemula SK, et al. Drug complexes: perspective from academic research and pharmaceutical market. *Pharm Res.* 2023;40(6):1519–40.
 17. Kim DH, Lee SE, Pyo YC, Tran P, Park JS. Solubility enhancement and application of cyclodextrins in local drug delivery. *J Pharm Investig.* 2020;50(1):17–27.
 18. Chaudhary VB, Patel JK. Cyclodextrin inclusion complex to enhance solubility of poorly water soluble drugs: A review. *Int J Pharm Sci Res.* 2013;4(1):68.
 19. Fenyvesi F, Pétervári M, Nagy L, Kéki S, Zsuga M, Bacskay L, et al. Solubility increasing experiments of silymarin with cyclodextrins. *J Med Aradean.* 2011;14(2):13–7.
 20. Nayak AK, Panigrahi PP. Solubility enhancement of etoricoxib by cosolvency approach. *ISRN Pharm.* 2012;2012:820653.
 21. Jouyban A. Review of the cosolvency models for predicting solubility of drugs in water-cosolvent mixtures. *J Pharm Pharm Sci.* 2008;11(1):32–58.
 22. Babu PS, Subrahmanyam CVS, Thimmasetty J, Manavalan R, Valliappan K, Kedarnath SA. Solubility enhancement of cox-II inhibitors by cosolvency approach. *Dhaka Univ J Pharm Sci.* 2008;7(2):119–26.
 23. Shao D, Yang Z, Zhou G, Chen J, Zheng S, Lv X, et al. Improving the solubility of acipimox by cosolvents and the study of thermodynamic properties on solvation process. *J Mol Liq.* 2018;262:389–95.
 24. Joshi J, Nainwal N, Saharan VA. Review on hydrotropy: A potential approach for the solubility enhancement of poorly soluble drug. *Asian J Pharm Clin Res.* 2019;12(10):19–26.
 25. Dhapte V, Mehta P. Advances in hydrotropic solutions: An updated review. *St. Petersburg Polytech Univ J Phys Math.* 2015;1(4):424–35.
 26. Agnihotri S. A review on mixed hydrotropy: solubility enhancement technique for poorly aqueous soluble drugs. *Int Res J Pharm.* 2020;11(9):31–8.
 27. Pradnya AP, Preeti PM. Titrimetric analysis of ibuprofen bulk drug sample by using urea as a hydrotropic solubilizing agent. *Int J Curr Pharm Res.* 2015;7(3):76–7.
 28. Maheshwari RK, Gupta J. New eco-friendly titrimetric analysis of frusemide tablets using mixed hydrotropic solubilisation. *Indian Drugs.* 2018;55(5):33–7.
 29. Ajay A, Deepak D, Jitesh K, Anjali N. Enhancement of solubility of poorly water

- soluble drug–metronidazole by hydrotrophy. *Asian J Pharm Res Dev.* 2013;1(2):98–102.
30. Kuchekar AB, Gawade A, Boldhane S. Hydrotropic solubilization: an emerging approach. *J Drug Deliv Ther.* 2021;11(1-s):200–6.
 31. Kalyani G, Bhuvanewari P, Hemalatha B, Padmalatha K. Hydrotrophy: a promising tool for solubility enhancement. *Asian J Pharm Technol.* 2022;12(2):146–50.
 32. Khan AD, Tabish M, Kaushik R, Saxena V, Kesharwani P, Gupta S, et al. Hydrotrophy: Recent advancements in enhancement of drug solubility and formulation development. *Int J Drug Deliv Technol.* 2021;11(2):652–60.
 33. Baytok N, Saka OM. Self emulsifying drug delivery systems—an overview. *J Fac Pharm Ankara Univ.* 2023;47(2):705–18.
 34. Tang JL, Sun J, He ZG. Self-emulsifying drug delivery systems: strategy for improving oral delivery of poorly soluble drugs. *Curr Drug Ther.* 2007;2(1):85–93.
 35. Salawi A. Self-emulsifying drug delivery systems: a novel approach to deliver drugs. *Drug Deliv.* 2022;29(1):1811–23.
 36. Ibrahim T, El-Megraba N, Abdallaha M. Self-emulsifying drug delivery formulations. *Zagazig J Pharm Sci.* 2018;27(1):1–21.
 37. Chaudhari S, Nikam SA, Khatri N, Wakde S. Co-crystals: a review. *J Drug Deliv Ther.* 2018;8(6-s):350–8.
 38. Rodríguez-Hornedo N, Nehm SJ, Jayasankar A. Cocrystals: design, properties and formation mechanisms. In: Swarbrick J, editor. *Encyclopedia of Pharmaceutical Technology.* New York: Informa Healthcare; 2007. p. 615–35.
 39. Emami S, Siahi-Shadbad M, Adibkia K, Barzegar-Jalali M. Recent advances in improving oral drug bioavailability by cocrystals. *BioImpacts.* 2018;8(4):305–14.
 40. Wicaksono Y, Wisudyarningsih B, Siswoyo TA. Enhancement of solubility and dissolution rate of atorvastatin calcium by co-crystallization. *Trop J Pharm Res.* 2017;16(7):1497–502.
 41. Alatas F, Ratih H, Soewandhi SN. Enhancement of solubility and dissolution rate of telmisartan by telmisartan-oxalic acid co-crystal formation. *Int J Pharm Pharm Sci.* 2015;7(2):423–6.
 42. Taniguchi C, Kawabata Y, Wada K, Yamada S, Onoue S. Microenvironmental pH-modification to improve dissolution behavior and oral absorption for drugs with pH-dependent solubility. *Expert Opin Drug Deliv.* 2014;11(4):505–16.
 43. Tran PHL, Tran TTD, Lee KH, Kim DJ, Lee BJ. Dissolution-modulating mechanism of pH modifiers in solid dispersion containing weakly acidic or basic drugs with poor water solubility. *Expert Opin Drug Deliv.* 2010;7(5):647–61.
 44. Li W, Yu J, Liu X, Zhang Y, Ji J, Wang H, et al. pH regulators for oral drug delivery. *Asian J Pharm Sci.* 2021;16(6):806–21.
 45. Trapani G, Franco M, Latrofa A, Sanna E, Biggio G, Liso G. Enhancement of GABA A receptor affinity and anticonvulsant activity of muscimol prodrugs. *Eur J Med Chem.* 1999;34(5):401–9.
 46. Aggarwal S, Gupta GD, Chaudhary S. Solubility enhancement of poorly water soluble drugs: a review. *Int J Drug Dev Res.* 2012;4(1):26–33.
 47. Ankit D, Sumit K, Shubhini S. Approaches to enhance solubility of poorly water-soluble drugs. *Int J Pharm Res Dev.* 2011;3(2):147–59.
 48. Morakul B, Prajapati ST, Thompson KL, Pentzer EB, Pinal R, Ierapetritou MG, et al. Integrated development of size-enlarged, stable amorphous drug nanoparticles for

- bioavailability enhancement of poorly water-soluble drugs. *Eur J Pharm Sci.* 2014;60:64–73.
49. Hecq J, Deleers M, Fanara D, Vranckx H, Amighi K. Preparation and characterization of nanocrystals for solubility and dissolution rate enhancement of nifedipine. *Int J Pharm.* 2005;299(1–2):167–77.
50. Chikhalia V, Gupta BP, Patel R, Dholakia D. Approaches for solubility enhancement of poorly water-soluble drugs. *Int J Pharm Sci Rev Res.* 2012;12(1):62–8.
51. Karole S, Shrivastava M, Thomas A. Solubility enhancement of poorly water-soluble drug by using hydrotropic agents. *Asian J Pharm.* 2019;13(1):16–22.
52. Prajapati SK, Tripathi P, Ubaidulla U, Anand V, Paliwal S. Solid dispersion: A strategy for solubility enhancement. *Pharma Times.* 2007;39(3):25–9.
53. Garala KC, Shinde AJ, Shah PH. Formulation and in-vitro characterization of lyophilised ranitidine hydrochloride fast dissolving tablets. *Rasayan J Chem.* 2009;2(1):244–52.
54. Patil V, Patil P, Patil H, Patil S, Dhabale P. Enhancement of solubility and dissolution rate of poorly water soluble drug by using novel solid dispersion. *Int J PharmTech Res.* 2011;3(3):1434–9.
55. Deshmukh A, Naik J. Solubility enhancement of rosuvastatin calcium by using different solubilization techniques. *Int J Pharm Sci Nanotechnol.* 2011;4(4):1511–5.
56. Ghanbarzadeh S, Valizadeh H, Zakeri-Milani P. The impact of spray-drying parameters on the physicochemical properties of celecoxib nanoparticles. *Adv Pharm Bull.* 2015;5(3):417–24.
57. Vehring R. Pharmaceutical particle engineering via spray drying. *Pharm Res.* 2008;25(5):999–1022.
58. Kaurav H, Hariharan M, Soni M. Solid dispersion: An approach for solubility enhancement. *J Adv Pharm Educ Res.* 2013;3(2):86–97.
59. Noyes AA, Whitney WR. The rate of solution of solid substances in their own solutions. *J Am Chem Soc.* 1897;19(12):930–4.

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